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Research Paper

In-Silico Drug Discovery of Flavonoids Targeting the Human Serotonin Transporter: A Multi-Approach Computational Study for Depression

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ABSTRACT

Background: Depression is a prevalent neuropsychiatric disorder characterized by serotonin (5-HT) deficiency, with the human serotonin transporter (hSERT) serving as a critical target for therapeutic intervention. Although selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) are widely prescribed, their clinical efficacy is often limited by adverse effects and treatment resistance. Flavonoids, a class of naturally occurring polyphenolic compounds, have demonstrated potential in modulating hSERT activity. This study employs a multi-faceted computational drug discovery approach to identify flavonoid-based hSERT inhibitors with enhanced binding affinity, pharmacokinetics, and stability. A comprehensive in-silico framework, incorporating molecular docking (Glide XP), ADMET profiling, MM-GBSA free energy calculations, and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, was utilized to screen and evaluate flavonoid candidates as prospective antidepressant agents. Results: Molecular docking analyses identified Globularicitrin as the most potent hSERT binder, exhibiting a docking score of -15.357, surpassing Fluoxetine (-10.306). ADMET predictions indicated optimal pharmacokinetic properties with a high probability (94-100%) of oral absorption. MM-GBSA calculations confirmed the stability of the Globularicitrin-hSERT complex, with a ΔG_{Bind} of -23.16 kcal/mol. MD simulations conducted over a 100-ns trajectory demonstrated stable RMSD values (2.0–2.4 Å) and sustained protein-ligand interactions, with ASP-98 (90% occupancy), ARG-104 (94%), and TYR-95 (86%) forming persistent hydrogen bonds within the binding pocket, further corroborating its

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structural stability. Conclusions: The computational findings indicate that Globularicitrin exhibits superior hSERT binding affinity, favorable pharmacokinetics, and robust structural stability compared to Fluoxetine. These results suggest that Globularicitrin represents a promising candidate for alternative antidepressant development, warranting further experimental validation to assess its therapeutic efficacy in preclinical and clinical applications.

INTRODUCTION

Depression is a chronic and debilitating neuropsychiatric disorder that affects over 280 million people worldwide, making it a leading cause of disability and a major contributor to the global disease burden[1]. Characterized by persistent sadness, loss of interest, cognitive impairment, and emotional dysregulation, depression significantly impacts an individual's social, occupational, and personal well-being[2]. The lifetime prevalence of major depressive disorder (MDD) is estimated between 10% and 20%, with a higher incidence in women. In India, one in every twenty individuals suffers from depression, a condition exacerbated by socioeconomic stressors, lifestyle changes, and increasing comorbidities like diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. Despite the availability of antidepressant treatments, 30%–50% of patients fail to achieve full remission, indicating a dire need for novel, more effective, and safer therapeutic alternatives[3, 4].

Central to the pathophysiology of depression is serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine, 5-HT) deficiency in the brain. The human serotonin transporter (hSERT) plays a pivotal role in regulating serotonergic neurotransmission by facilitating serotonin reuptake from the synaptic cleft into presynaptic neurons, thus terminating its signaling[5]. As a critical therapeutic target, hSERT is the primary site of action for selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), which function by blocking serotonin reuptake and enhancing serotonergic activity. However, SSRIs

and serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs) like fluoxetine, sertraline, venlafaxine, and duloxetine suffer from several limitations, including delayed onset of action, adverse side effects (such as sexual dysfunction, weight gain, sleep disturbances), treatment resistance, increased suicidal risk in younger populations, and withdrawal symptoms[6]. These drawbacks emphasize the need for novel antidepressant strategies that offer enhanced efficacy, faster onset, and reduced side effects.

Flavonoids, a diverse class of plant-derived polyphenolic compounds, have garnered significant attention for their potential antidepressant properties. Found in fruits, vegetables, and medicinal plants, flavonoids have demonstrated the ability to modulate monoaminergic neurotransmission, reduce oxidative stress, and promote neuronal survival. Certain flavonoids, such as quercetin, kaempferol, and baicalein, have shown promise in inhibiting hSERT, suggesting their potential as natural antidepressants[7]. These compounds offer several advantages over synthetic antidepressants, including their natural origin, multi-target mechanisms, lower toxicity, and fewer side effects. Additionally, flavonoids have demonstrated fast-acting antidepressant-like effects in preclinical models[8]. Despite these promising findings, the molecular interactions of flavonoids with hSERT remain largely unexplored, which underscores the need for further investigation using advanced computational drug discovery techniques.

1.1. In-Silico Approach for Flavonoid-Based hSERT Inhibition

In this study, we employ a multi-approach in-silico strategy to evaluate the potential of flavonoids as hSERT inhibitors, leveraging the power of computational drug discovery. Using the crystal structure of hSERT (PDB ID: 5I6X), our workflow

integrates molecular docking, pharmacokinetic profiling, binding free energy calculations, and molecular dynamics simulations to identify promising flavonoid candidates. **Molecular Docking** – This technique is used to assess the binding affinities and interaction patterns of flavonoids within the hSERT active site[9]. The docking process helps predict how these compounds interact with key amino acid residues responsible for serotonin reuptake inhibition. **ADMET Screening** – The absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) properties of flavonoids are analyzed to evaluate their pharmacokinetic profile and drug-likeness, ensuring that selected compounds have favourable bioavailability and minimal toxicity. **MM/GBSA Calculations** – Molecular Mechanics/Generalized Born Surface Area (MM/GBSA) calculations are performed to estimate the binding free energy of flavonoid-hSERT complexes, providing a more accurate measure of binding stability and affinity. **Molecular Dynamics (MD) Simulations** – To analyze the stability and dynamic behaviour of flavonoid-hSERT interactions over time, MD simulations are conducted under physiological conditions. This step ensures that the identified flavonoids form stable and sustained interactions with hSERT, which is crucial for their potential antidepressant effects[10].

All computational analyses are performed using Schrödinger 2023-1, a state-of-the-art software suite for structure-based drug discovery. By integrating these in-silico methodologies, we aim to identify novel flavonoid-based hSERT inhibitors with high binding affinity, favourable pharmacokinetics, and stable interactions. Our findings could pave the way for the development of safer, naturally derived antidepressant agents that overcome the limitations of current treatments. Ultimately, this study provides valuable insights into flavonoid-hSERT

interactions, contributing to the rational design of antidepressant therapies that offer improved efficacy, reduced side effects, and enhanced patient outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Protein preparation:

The (hSERT) protein (PDB ID: 5I6X) was retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank and prepared for molecular modelling using the Protein Preparation Wizard in Schrödinger Suite 2023-1. The preprocessing step involved removing crystallographic water molecules and adding missing side chains and hydrogen atoms to ensure structural integrity. Bond orders were assigned appropriately, and the most probable protonation states for ionizable residues were determined under physiological conditions. The structure was then subjected to energy minimization using the OPLS4 force field, where side-chain hydroxyl groups were optimized, and heavy atoms were converged to an RMSD of 0.30 Å. Restraints were applied to maintain the backbone conformation while allowing local flexibility for improved stability. The active site was identified, and a grid box was generated to define the binding pocket for subsequent docking studies[11, 12].

2.2. Ligand preparation

The phytochemical structures were processed using the LigPrep module of Schrödinger Suite 2023-1 to ensure high-quality molecular structures suitable for docking studies. The Epik module was employed to generate ionization states, tautomeric forms, and desalted structures at a physiological pH of 7.0 ± 2.0 , ensuring that each compound was represented in its most relevant protonation state. This step is critical for accurate binding affinity predictions, as improper charge states can significantly affect ligand-receptor interactions. During LigPrep processing, the structures

underwent stereochemical refinement, where specified chiralities were retained, and unnecessary counterions or solvent molecules were removed. Additionally, alternative stereoisomers were generated where applicable to account for potential biological relevance. The geometry optimization was performed using the OPLS4 force field within the Impact package of Schrödinger, allowing for energy minimization while preserving the correct molecular conformation. This step ensures that ligands adopt a stable and low-energy state, crucial for reliable docking and binding studies.

The energy minimization process was executed until a root mean square deviation (RMSD) of 1.8 Å was achieved, refining atomic positions to eliminate steric clashes and ensure structural stability. For molecules containing flexible rings, a single low-energy ring conformation was generated to maintain biological relevance while reducing excessive computational complexity during docking. The final optimized phytochemicals were thoroughly analyzed to confirm correct stereochemistry, protonation states, and overall molecular integrity before proceeding to docking analysis. These well-prepared ligand structures enhance the accuracy of molecular docking by ensuring that only biologically relevant conformations are used, ultimately improving predictions of ligand-receptor interactions and potential drug-like behaviour[13, 14].

2.3. Receptor grid generation

The Receptor Grid Generation Wizard in Schrödinger was used to define the docking region within the prepared protein structure. A grid box was created at the centroid of the active site with coordinates $x = -32.92$, $y = -21.86$, $z = 1.68$, ensuring precise ligand docking. The Van der Waals (VdW) scaling factor was set to 1.0 for the receptor, while a partial charge cutoff of 0.25 was

applied. To accommodate ligand flexibility, the grid dimensions were expanded appropriately to cover the entire binding site without introducing unnecessary computational overhead. Additionally, constraints such as hydrogen bonding and metal coordination were applied as needed, and excluded volumes were defined to restrict docking to relevant regions. Electrostatic and hydrophobic site maps were also incorporated to improve docking accuracy. The final receptor grid was validated to ensure it accurately represented the binding pocket, optimizing docking efficiency for subsequent virtual screening and drug discovery studies[15, 16].

2.4. Molecular docking studies using Glide:

The phytochemicals obtained from the LigPrep module were docked using the Glide module of the Schrödinger suite 2023-1 in Extra Precision (XP) mode to achieve highly accurate binding affinity predictions. The best Glide G-scores were selected based on their ability to balance various molecular interactions, punishing steric conflicts while promoting favourable lipophilic, hydrogen bonding, and metal-ligand interactions. The docking results were analyzed using the XP Visualizer, which provided detailed insights into the molecular interactions at the receptor site. The Glide scores of the phytochemicals were compared with those of commonly used antidepressant medications, such as Fluoxetine, to evaluate their potential efficacy. Several docking factors influenced the scoring, including lipophilic perseverance, where ligands are deeply enclosed within the hydrophobic pocket, enhancing their stability. Additionally, electrostatic interactions, hydrogen bonding, and π - π stacking interactions played a crucial role in strengthening ligand-receptor binding. The binding affinity could also be enhanced by metal coordination and water-mediated hydrogen bonding in some cases. However, unfavourable factors such as rotational

penalties, desolvation energy penalties, and steric clashes could negatively impact the Glide score. The presence of excessive ligand flexibility also led to higher penalties, reducing docking accuracy[11, 17].

2.5. ADMET profile:

The ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) profile of the phytochemicals was analyzed using the QikProp module in the Schrödinger suite 2023-1. This computational approach provided insights into key physicochemical and pharmacokinetic properties, which are essential for evaluating the drug-likeness and oral bioavailability of the compounds. Various descriptors were predicted, including molecular weight, hydrogen bond acceptor and donor count, partition coefficient (log P), total solvent-accessible surface area (SASA), and molar volume. The Lipinski's Rule of Five was assessed to determine drug-like properties, and the number of violations was recorded to ensure compliance with oral drug delivery standards. Additionally, aqueous solubility (log S), van der Waals volume, and human oral absorption percentage were predicted to assess the compounds' solubility, permeability, and overall bioavailability[18, 19].

2.6. Molecular Dynamics studies:

Molecular Dynamics (MD) Simulation Protocol Using Desmond

The molecular dynamics (MD) simulation was conducted using Desmond in the Schrödinger suite 2023-1, following a structured protocol to ensure accuracy and reproducibility. The initial biomolecular structure protein was obtained in PDB format and pre-processed using Maestro 13.5 to add missing atoms or residues, assign protonation states at physiological pH (7.4), and optimize hydrogen bonding networks. For ligand-

containing systems, LigPrep was used to generate parameters, validated against the OPLS4 force field. The system was solvated using the TIP3P - Transferable Intermolecular Potential and widely used three-site water model in molecular dynamics simulations, designed to accurately represent the physical and chemical properties of water model within an orthorhombic simulation box, maintaining a 10 Å buffer distance around the solute. To neutralize the system and achieve an ionic concentration of 0.15 M NaCl, Na⁺ or Cl⁻ ions were added using the System Builder tool in Maestro. The OPLS4 force field was applied, and non-standard residues or ligands were validated. The Desmond Setup Wizard was used to configure the NPT ensemble, maintaining a temperature of 300 K and pressure of 1 atm for a 100 ns simulation. The system underwent three equilibration steps: energy minimization using the steepest descent algorithm to eliminate steric clashes, a short-restrained MD simulation (100 ns) to allow solvent relaxation, and a brief unrestrained MD simulation (1 ns) to equilibrate the full system. The 100 ns production run was executed on a high-performance computing (HPC) cluster, saving trajectory frames every 10 ps for further analysis[16].

Post-simulation analysis was carried out using tools from the Schrödinger suite, including root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) to assess protein backbone stability, root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF) to evaluate residue flexibility, and hydrogen bond analysis to identify key interactions. Additionally, MM/GBSA binding free energy calculations were performed to estimate ligand binding affinities. The trajectory and interactions were visualized using Maestro, providing insights into conformational changes, ligand binding mechanisms, and solvent effects. This workflow ensures a robust and reproducible MD simulation process, enabling a detailed

exploration of biomolecular systems at atomic resolution[20, 21].

2.7. Binding Free Energy Estimation Using Prime/MM-GBSA:

The binding free energy of the phytochemicals was estimated using the Prime MM-GBSA module in the Schrödinger suite 2023-1. The OPLS4 force field was applied to minimize the energy of the XP-docked ligand-receptor complex, ensuring an optimized conformation. The Generalized Born/Surface Area (GB/SA) model with VSGB 2.0 (Variable-dielectric Surface Generalized Born) solvent mode was used to estimate the solvation free energy of the molecule in the given solvent. The Prime MM-GBSA binding free energy (ΔG_{bind}) was determined using the following equation:

$$\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = E_{\text{complex (minimized)}} - (E_{\text{receptor (minimized)}} + E_{\text{ligand (minimized)}})$$

This calculation provided a quantitative measure of ligand binding affinity, aiding in the identification of potential lead compounds for further experimental validation[11, 22].

RESULTS

3.1 Comprehensive in Silico ADMET Screening of Bioactive Compounds Using the QikProp Module:

The ADMET screening of the compounds was performed in silico using the QikProp module of the Schrödinger Suite 2023-1. The results of the ADMET properties for the compounds are summarized in Table 1. Based on the Insilco screening, most compounds exhibit properties within the recommended limits. All parameters were evaluated according to the recommended range limits specified in the QikProp Module User Manual 4.4. Additionally, a comprehensive list of all ADMET parameters is provided in Supplementary Data Table 1. The molecular weight of the compounds ranges from 254.242 to 610.568. The predicted octanol/water partition coefficient (QPlogPo/w) falls within -2.35 to 4.62, while the predicted IC50 value for HERG K+ channel blockade ranges from -3.428 to -5.99. The predicted brain/blood partition coefficient (QPlogBB) varies between -4.58 and 0.74. Additionally, the predicted qualitative human oral absorption is within the recommended limits. The number of violations of Lipinski's Rule of Five for most compounds falls between 0 and 3. The compounds also exhibit excellent human oral absorption, with values ranging from 94% to 100%. Overall, the in silico ADMET screening indicates that most compounds meet the recommended criteria, with only a few parameters deviating for certain compounds.

Table 1: Detailed Prediction of ADMET Properties for Various Flavonoids Using the QikProp Module

S.No	Entry Name	mol MW	QPlog P o/w	QPlog HERG	QPlogBB	Human oral Absorption	Rule of Five
1	Globularicitrin	610.524	-2.34	-5.607	-4.564	1	3
2	kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether -3-O-Beta-D-Gluco pyranoside	594.525	-2.031	-5.699	-4.584	1	3
3	Isoquercetin	464.382	-1.609	-5.284	-3.989	1	2
4	hesperidin	610.568	-1.473	-5.81	-4.266	1	3
5	Hyperoside	464.382	-1.167	-5.072	-3.525	1	2
6	Fluoxetine	309.331	4.623	-5.996	0.742	3	0
7	Naringin	580.541	-1.641	-4.496	-3.143	1	3
8	Fiestin	286.24	0.484	-4.956	-1.832	3	0

9	Scutellarin	462.366	-0.218	-4.154	-3.987	1	2
10	Miquelianin	478.365	-0.932	-3.428	-4.102	1	2
11	isorhamnetin	316.267	1.18	-4.87	-1.844	3	0
12	luteolin	286.24	0.962	-5.026	-1.935	3	0
13	Vitexin	432.383	-0.698	-5.526	-3.292	2	1
14	Apigenin	270.241	1.654	-5.18	-1.451	3	0
15	chrysin	254.242	2.39	-5.265	-0.877	3	0
16	cynaroside	448.382	-1.033	-5.656	-3.763	1	2
17	naringenin	272.257	1.632	-4.951	-1.377	3	0
18	kamepferol	286.24	1.014	-4.909	-1.747	3	0
19	Myricetin	318.239	-0.318	-4.676	-2.732	2	1
20	Quercetin	302.24	0.33	-4.767	-2.242	2	0
21	ombuin	330.293	2.02	-5.058	-1.462	3	0
22	baicalin	446.367	0.472	-3.813	-3.039	1	2
23	quercitrin	448.382	-0.684	-5.237	-3.26	2	2
24	wogonin	284.268	2.61	-5.097	-0.822	3	0
25	Nobiletin	402.4	3.552	-4.909	-0.2	3	0

3.2. Molecular Docking Analysis and Binding Interactions of Flavonoids with (hSERT)

In Schrödinger 2023-1 (Maestro 13.5), molecular docking was performed using Extra Precision (XP) mode, which provides a more accurate assessment of ligand-protein interactions by incorporating advanced scoring functions and penalties for non-ideal interactions. The docking results revealed a root mean square deviation (RMSD) of 0.2 for the molecules, indicating an excellent fit and high reliability of the predicted binding conformations. Molecular docking analysis was conducted to evaluate the interaction and binding affinity of selected ligands against the human serotonin transporter (hSERT). Among the tested compounds, the results are summarized in **Table 2**, where all flavonoids were docked into the same binding pocket using Extra Precision (XP) mode. Globularicitrin exhibited the highest docking score (-15.357), indicating a strong binding interaction, whereas Fluoxetine, a standard drug, showed a lower docking score of (-10.306). These results suggest that Globularicitrin has a stronger binding potential at the active site. The enhanced binding affinity of Globularicitrin is primarily attributed to multiple hydrogen bonds, electrostatic

interactions, and extensive hydrophobic contacts, contributing to its stability within the binding pocket. The 2D interaction analysis revealed that Globularicitrin forms strong hydrogen bonds with key residues ASP-98, GLN-332, and SER-336, along with π - π stacking interactions with PHE-335 and additional hydrophobic contacts with TYR-95, ALA-169, and LEU-434 are given in **figure 1**. In contrast, Fluoxetine primarily relies on hydrophobic interactions with TYR-95, LEU-99, and PHE-341 and forms only a single hydrogen bond with ASN-177, leading to a comparatively lower binding affinity and reduced stability within the active site are given in **figure 2**. The higher docking score of Globularicitrin suggests a more stable and deeply penetrating interaction with hSERT, whereas Fluoxetine's weaker electrostatic interactions and limited hydrogen bonding contribute to its lower stability. These findings indicate that Globularicitrin may serve as a more effective ligand for hSERT modulation due to its superior interaction profile. However, further studies, including molecular dynamics simulations, has been validated its potential as a novel hSERT inhibitor as detailed in the following section. The 3D and 2D docking interaction images of Globularicitrin and Fluoxetine are

presented in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. The docking results of other flavonoids, including their interaction profiles, are provided in the Supplementary File for further reference.

Fig:1 The above figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid Globularicitrin with Human Serotonin Transporter (5I6X).

Fig:2 The above figure represents Ligand interaction of standard drug Fluoxetine with Human Serotonin Transporter (5I6X).

Table 2: Tabular Representation of XP Docking Scores for In-Silico Screening of Flavonoids Against Human Serotonin Transporter (PDB ID: 5I6X)

S. No	Structure ID	Entry Name	docking score	XP G Score	glide G score	glide emodel
1	5280805	Globularicitrin	-15.357	-15.393	-15.393	-60.942

2	5318767	kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether -3-O-Beta-D-Gluco pyranoside	-14.13	-14.165	-14.165	-70.467
3	5480505	Isoquercetin	-13.208	-13.242	-13.242	-75.535
4	10621	hesperidin	-13.048	-13.048	-13.048	-19.262
5	5281643	Hyperoside	-10.76	-10.796	-10.796	-100.542
6	3386	Fluoxetine	-10.306	-10.307	-10.307	-67.83
7	442428	Naringin	-10.215	-10.215	-10.215	-19.602
8	496032 302	Fiestin	-9.993	-10.031	-10.031	-55.027
9	185617	Scutellarin	-9.846	-9.852	-9.852	-63.129
10	5274585	Miquelianin	-9.702	-9.738	-9.738	-74.624
11	5281654	isorhamnetin	-9.634	-9.673	-9.673	-58.395
12	5280445	luteolin	-9.499	-9.547	-9.547	-55.868
13	5280441	Vitexin	-9.165	-9.208	-9.208	-73.636
14	5280443	Apigenin	-9.154	-9.202	-9.202	-60.754
15	5281607	chrysin	-9.14	-9.192	-9.192	-47.702
16	5280637	cynaroside	-9.034	-9.034	-9.034	-75.339
17	439246	naringenin	-8.969	-8.992	-8.992	-51.331
18	5280863	kamepferol	-8.859	-8.898	-8.898	-54.077
19	5281672	Myricetin	-8.842	-8.888	-8.888	-69.547
20	5280343	Quercetin	-8.807	-8.847	-8.847	-58.382
21	5320287	ombuin	-8.707	-8.718	-8.718	-59.372
22	5281703	wogonin	-8.442	-8.486	-8.486	-58.814
23	64982	baicalin	-8.404	-8.414	-8.414	-68.512
24	5280459	quercitrin	-7.519	-7.555	-7.555	-78.117
25	72344	Nobiletin	-0.548	-0.548	-0.548	-64.306

3.3. Binding Free Energy Calculation Using the Prime/MM-GBSA Approach

The stability of the docking complex was assessed using MM-GBSA free energy calculations as a post-scoring approach following molecular docking with the human serotonin transporter (hSERT), with values presented in Table 3. The dG_{Bind} values ranged from -44.83 to 21.64 kcal/mol, dG_{Coulomb} values varied between -54.26 and 7.1 kcal/mol, and $dG_{\text{hydrogen bond}}$ contributions were between -5.03 and -0.25 kcal/mol, with binding energy positively contributing to the total energy. The lowest energy poses of the scoring function confirmed the stability of the docking complex, with G-scores closely aligning with experimentally determined binding energies from X-ray crystallography. The G-score and MM-GBSA energy values within the

active site further supported the stability of the docking interactions. To evaluate binding stability, MM-GBSA calculations showed Globularicitrin exhibited a ΔG_{Bind} of -23.16 kcal/mol, whereas Fluoxetine had a more favorable ΔG_{Bind} of -40.86 kcal/mol. Further decomposition of the MM-GBSA results indicated that Globularicitrin had a significant Coulombic energy contribution (-54.26 kcal/mol), supporting strong electrostatic interactions, whereas Fluoxetine's Coulombic energy was much lower (-1.47 kcal/mol), implying that van der Waals and hydrophobic interactions played a more dominant role in its binding. Additionally, hydrogen bonding contributions were -5.03 kcal/mol for Globularicitrin and -0.65 kcal/mol for Fluoxetine, confirming that Globularicitrin formed stronger hydrogen bonds than Fluoxetine.

Table 3: Binding Free Energy Calculations of flavonoids Using the Prime/MM-GBSA Approach

Entry Name	Prime Energy	MMGBSA dG Bind	MMGBSA dG Bind Coulomb	MMGBSA dG Bind Covalent	MMGBSA dG Bind Hbond
Globularicitrin	-35299.5	-23.16	-54.26	26.01	-5.03
kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether -3-O-Beta-D-Glucopyranoside	-35328	-29.32	-52.38	20.64	-4.14
Isoquercetin	-35355.6	-44.83	-25.41	5.18	-2.57
hesperidin	-35151.4	18.05	-27.58	19.54	-3.81
Hyperoside	-35325.8	-18.1	-19.27	6.64	-3.16
Fluoxetine	-35150.8	-40.86	-1.47	0.84	-0.65
Naringin	-35181.9	14.74	-30.16	12.03	-2.95
Fiestin	-35257.7	-26.37	-12.25	7.15	-0.98
Scutellarin	-35257.1	21.64	-0.55	14.56	-2.11
Miquelianin	-35321.4	-7.25	-30.47	15.27	-2.99
isorhamnetin	-35345.9	-29.16	-3.14	7.74	-1.34
luteolin	-35438.7	-27.97	2.33	3.71	-1.22
Vitexin	-35410.5	-18.03	-18.98	6.14	-2.29
Apigenin	-35469.3	-28.98	-12.9	3.71	-1.25
chrysin	-35418.6	-18.4	-8.91	8.05	-0.92
cynaroside	-35333.7	-11.17	-13.9	7.71	-1.72
naringenin	-35318.9	-19.74	-7.39	4.16	-0.72
kameferol	-35371.4	-24.68	-1.16	2.67	-0.8
Myricetin	-35364.6	-30.73	-24.52	-0.05	-2.3
Quercetin	-35363.4	-30.7	-8.08	7.13	-1.89
ombuin	-35327.3	-44.1	-8.28	-0.96	-0.56
wogonin	-35358.6	-29.4	7.1	3.05	-0.25
baicalin	-35254.8	-5.1	-20.22	13.93	-3
quercitrin	-35336.2	-23.16	-28.39	9.21	-3
Nobiletin	-35219	-34.81	-12.02	5.57	-0.51

3.4. Molecular Dynamics stimulations:

Structural Stability Analysis - Protein Stability and RMSD Analysis:

The Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) analysis was performed to assess the stability of 5I6X after Globularicitrin binding. The RMSD of C α atoms showed fluctuations between 1.8 and 2.9 Å, indicating a relatively stable protein structure. The stabilization of RMSD towards the later stages of the trajectory confirms that the system reached equilibrium, ensuring the reliability of further structural and interaction analyses. Minor fluctuations observed suggest localized conformational changes, but the overall protein

structure remained intact, validating the stability of the ligand-protein complex as given in figure 3.

Figure 3: Demonstrates Structural Stability Analysis - Protein Stability and Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) Analysis

Ligand Stability and RMSD Analysis:

The ligand RMSD was analyzed to determine the stability of Globularicitrin in the 5I6X binding pocket. The initial fluctuations between 1.6 and 2.8 Å indicate that the ligand was adjusting to the binding site. However, after 18-25 ns, the ligand stabilized in the range of 2.0 to 2.4 Å, maintaining this conformation for the remainder of the simulation. This suggests that Globularicitrin remained bound within the active site without significant displacement, confirming its strong binding affinity as shown in figure 3. A stable ligand RMSD relative to the protein backbone indicates that the ligand maintained a consistent binding orientation, which is crucial for potential drug candidates.

Protein Flexibility and RMSF Analysis:

The Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF) was used to assess local flexibility in the 5I6X protein. Most of the protein exhibited low RMSF values, indicating high structural stability. However, residues 120-140 showed higher fluctuations (~3.5 Å), corresponding to loop regions, which are inherently more flexible. Another fluctuation peak was observed in the 420-520 residue range, suggesting localized dynamic movements. Despite these fluctuations, the overall structure remained stable, ensuring a secure ligand-binding environment as shown in figure 4. The interaction of Globularicitrin with rigid regions of the protein further reinforces the stability of the protein-ligand complex.

Figure 4: Root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF) of the simulated protein 5I6X in complex with Globularicitrin during a 100 ns molecular dynamics (MD) simulation.

Protein Secondary Structure Stability:

The secondary structure analysis of the protein during the simulation revealed that alpha-helices and beta-strands were largely maintained throughout the 100 ns trajectory, ensuring that the protein did not undergo major conformational changes. The percentage of secondary structure elements (SSE) remained at ~59.2%, with 58.54% helices and 0.66% strands, confirming that the protein retained its native structure after ligand binding as Visualized in figure 5.

Figure 5 Illustrated Protein secondary structure elements (SSE) like alpha-helices and beta-strands are monitored throughout the simulation.

The stable secondary structure distribution supports the idea that Globularicitrin does not destabilize the 5I6X transporter, making it a promising candidate for further studies.

Protein-Ligand Interaction Analysis:

The protein-ligand interaction analysis revealed multiple stabilizing forces, including hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interactions, ionic interactions, and water bridges. The most persistent hydrogen bonds were observed with ASP 98 (90% occupancy), ARG 104 (94%), and TYR 95 (86%), indicating their significant role in ligand stabilization. Hydrophobic interactions were frequent with TYR 95, ALA 169, and TYR 175, reinforcing ligand positioning within the active pocket. Furthermore, water-bridged interactions were prominent with ASN 177, PHE 334, and TRP 103, suggesting that solvent molecules contribute to the ligand's stability in the binding site as Presented in given figure 6 & 7.

Figure 6: Interaction fraction of the 5I6X protein complexed with Globularicitrin during a 100 ns molecular dynamics (MD) simulation.

Figure 7: Timeline representation of various contacts formed by Globularicitrin in complex with the 5I6X protein during a 100 ns molecular dynamics (MD) simulation.

Interaction Timeline and Stability:

The interaction timeline analysis confirmed that key residues maintained stable interactions with the ligand. SER 336 exhibited interaction for the first 20 ns, lost contact temporarily, and regained it from 60-100 ns, suggesting a transient binding pattern. In contrast, LEU 337 and GLY 435 did not participate in significant interactions. The 2D ligand interaction diagram indicated that ASP 98, ARG 104, and TYR 95 consistently engaged in hydrogen bonding, while hydrophobic and water-mediated interactions remained stable throughout the simulation. The strong and persistent interactions suggest a high binding affinity of Globularicitrin for 5I6X, reinforcing its potential as a SERT transporter inhibitor as outlined in figure 8.

Figure 8: 2D interaction diagram of Globularicitrin in complex with the 5I6X protein during the 100 ns MD simulation trajectory of the protein-ligand complex.

Ligand Conformational Analysis and Torsion Profile:

The ligand RMSF analysis provided insights into atom-level fluctuations, revealing minimal changes, which suggests that Globularicitrin maintained its binding conformation without excessive movement. The torsional analysis of the ligand confirmed that the rotatable bonds remained stable, preventing major entropic penalties and reinforcing a well-fitted docking pose. Additionally, the ligand's molecular surface area (MolSA), solvent-accessible surface area (SASA), and polar surface area (PSA) remained consistent, indicating that the ligand did not undergo significant conformational strain as represented in figure 9.

Figure 9 represents the ligand properties, including ligand RMSD, radius of gyration (rGyr), intramolecular hydrogen bonds (intraHB), molecular surface area (MolSA), solvent-accessible surface area (SASA), and polar surface area (PSA), were analyzed. Additionally, the root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF) of both the ligand and protein in complex with 5I6X was evaluated during the 100 ns molecular dynamics (MD) simulation.

DISCUSSION

The in-silico evaluation of flavonoid-based inhibitors for hSERT revealed Globularicitrin as a promising candidate, exhibiting superior binding affinity and stability compared to the standard SSRI, Fluoxetine. Molecular docking analysis in XP mode yielded a significantly higher docking score (-15.357) for Globularicitrin versus Fluoxetine (-10.306), suggesting enhanced ligand-receptor complementarity. ADMET profiling confirmed its favorable pharmacokinetic properties, including optimal oral bioavailability (94–100%) and adherence to Lipinski's Rule of Five. MM-GBSA free energy calculations (-23.16 kcal/mol) indicated thermodynamic stability of the Globularicitrin-hSERT complex, supported by favorable Coulombic and hydrogen bonding contributions. Molecular dynamics simulations over a 100 ns trajectory further validated its

stability, with RMSD fluctuations confined to 2.0–2.4 Å and consistent hydrogen bonding interactions with key residues ASP-98 (90%), ARG-104 (94%), and TYR-95 (86%). Secondary structure analysis demonstrated minimal conformational perturbations, reinforcing the structural integrity of hSERT upon ligand binding. Collectively, these findings position Globularicitrin as a potent natural modulator of serotonin reuptake, necessitating further biochemical and preclinical investigations to elucidate its antidepressant potential.

CONCLUSION:

This study presents a computational framework for the rational design of flavonoid-based serotonin transporter (hSERT) inhibitors as potential antidepressant agents. A multi-tiered in-silico strategy, integrating molecular docking, ADMET profiling, MM-GBSA binding free energy calculations, and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, identified Globularicitrin as a lead candidate with superior binding affinity and stability compared to Fluoxetine. The structural and energetic analyses revealed key interaction patterns, including hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic contacts, contributing to its inhibitory potential. ADMET screening confirmed its favorable pharmacokinetic and safety profile, reinforcing its drug-likeness. The study provides mechanistic insights into flavonoid-hSERT interactions, supporting the development of naturally derived antidepressants with improved therapeutic indices. The 100 ns molecular dynamics simulation demonstrated that Globularicitrin binds stably within the 5I6X binding site, with strong hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic contacts, and water bridges supporting its binding affinity. The protein structure remained stable, showing only minor fluctuations in loop regions, while the ligand maintained its binding pose with minimal RMSD

deviations. The persistent interactions of ASP 98, ARG 104, and TYR 95 suggest that Globularicitrin could effectively target the SERT transporter, making it a strong candidate for further experimental validation and optimization of flavonoid-based hSERT inhibitors in preclinical and clinical Applications.

Abbreviations

MDD – Major Depressive Disorder

hSERT – Human Serotonin Transporter

SSRI – Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitor

SNRI – Serotonin-Norepinephrine Reuptake Inhibitor

ADMET – Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity

MM/GBSA – Molecular Mechanics/Generalized Born Surface Area

MD – Molecular Dynamics

HT – 5-Hydroxytryptamine (Serotonin)

PDB – Protein Data Bank

XP – Extra Precision (used in molecular docking)

ΔG_{bind} – Binding Free Energy in Prime/MM-GBSA calculations

VSGB – Variable-dielectric Surface Generalized Born (solvent model in Prime)

OPLS4 – Optimized Potentials for Liquid Simulations (Force Field used in Prime calculations)

dG_{Coulomb} – Electrostatic Energy Contribution in Prime/MM-GBSA

dG_{Hbond} – Hydrogen Bond Energy Contribution in Prime/MM-GBSA

dG_{Bind Covalent} – Covalent Energy Contribution in Prime/MM-GBSA

Prime Energy – Total Energy of the Ligand-Receptor Complex in Prime

G-score – Glide Score (used in docking before Prime/MM-GBSA refinement)

Clinical trial number: not applicable.

Ethics approval and consent to participate- Not applicable

Human Ethics and Consent to Participate declarations-NOT APPLICABLE.

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FIGURE LEGEND: Molecular docking results using Glide Module (XP- precision)

1. The below figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid **Globalaricitrin** with Human Serotonin Transporter (5I6X) dock score (-15.357)

2. The below figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether -3-O-Beta-D-Gluco pyranoside with Human Serotonin Transporter (5I6X) dock score (-14.13)

3. The below figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid Isoquercetin with Human Serotonin Transporter (5I6X) dock score (-13.208)

4. The below figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid hesperidin with Human Serotonin Transporter (5I6X) dock score (-13.048)

5. The below figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid Hyperoside with Human Serotonin Transporter (5I6X) dock score (-10.76)

6. The below figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid **Fluoxetine** with Human Serotonin Transporter (5I6X) dock score (-10.306)

9. The below figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid Scutellarin with Human Serotonin Transporter (516X) dock score (-9.846)

10. The below figure represents Ligand interaction of flavonoid Miquelianin with Human Serotonin Transporter (516X) dock score (-9.702)

Table legend: ADMET Profile

A comprehensive list of all ADMET parameters is provided according to the recommended range limits specified in the QikProp Module User Manual 4.4

S. No	Title	Entry Name	#stars	#amine	#amidine	#acid	#amide	#rotor	#rtvFG	CNS	mol MW	dipole	SASA	FOSA
1	5280805	Globularicitrin	9	0	0	0	0	15	2	-2	610.524	10.895	820.501	232.964
2	5318767	kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether - 3-O-Beta-D- Glucopyranoside	8	0	0	0	0	14	2	-2	594.525	10.195	817.802	197.595
3	5480505	Isoquercetin	4	0	0	0	0	11	1	-2	464.382	7.381	670.533	71.009
4	10621	hesperidin	8	0	0	0	0	14	2	-2	610.568	9.944	860.195	336.236
5	5281643	Hyperoside	4	0	0	0	0	11	1	-2	464.382	2.639	667.914	91.934
6	3386	Fluoxetine	0	1	0	0	0	6	0	2	309.331	5.058	562.905	156.922
7	442428	Naringin	5	0	0	0	0	13	2	-2	580.541	8.553	715.357	214.92
8	496032302	Fiestin	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	-2	286.24	4.76	496.822	0
9	185617	Scutellarin	3	0	0	1	0	9	1	-2	462.366	6.898	696.441	57.521
10	5274585	Miquelianin	3	0	0	1	0	10	1	-2	478.365	6.617	667.449	63.19
11	5281654	isorhamnetin	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	-2	316.267	6.044	530.868	90.414
12	5280445	luteolin	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	-2	286.24	8.125	502.733	0
13	5280441	Vitexin	3	0	0	0	0	8	0	-2	432.383	9.737	666.416	90.403
14	5280443	Apigenin	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	-2	270.241	6.353	494.238	0
15	5281607	chrysin	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	-1	254.242	4.589	480.748	0
16	5280637	cynaroside	2	0	0	0	0	10	1	-2	448.382	6.038	687.148	111.048
17	439246	naringenin	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	-2	272.257	4.526	497.214	51.547
18	5280863	kameferol	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	-2	286.24	3.603	492.701	0
19	5281672	Myricetin	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	-2	318.239	1.768	512.597	0
20	5280343	Quercetin	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	-2	302.24	4.064	501.872	0
21	5320287	ombuin	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	-2	330.293	7.084	564.351	185.525
22	5281703	wogonin	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	-1	284.268	6.289	507.421	82.697
23	64982	baicalin	1	0	0	1	0	8	1	-2	446.367	7.367	659.713	64.552
24	5280459	quercitrin	2	0	0	0	0	9	1	-2	448.382	7.058	657.229	120.582
25	5281703	wogonin	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	-1	284.268	3.521	511.102	83.04
26	72344	Nobiletin	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	402.4	5.358	655.252	478.586

Entry Name	FISA	PISA	WPSA	volume	donorHB	accptHB	dip ² /V	ACxDN ⁵ /SA	glob	QPpolrz	QPlogPC16	QPlogPoct
Globularicitrin	406.884	180.653	0	1585.47	9	20.55	0.07487	0.07514	0.80141	49.39	19.106	42.644
kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether - 3-O-Beta-D- Glucopyranoside	415.927	204.28	0	1581.47	8	19.8	0.06572	0.06848	0.80271	50.098	19.066	41.029
Isoquercetin	399.201	200.323	0	1228.25	7	13.75	0.04435	0.05425	0.82719	37.851	15.444	31.708
hesperidin	365.827	158.133	0	1641.17	7	20.05	0.06026	0.06167	0.78223	52.046	18.827	39.912
Hyperoside	365.404	210.577	0	1256.87	7	13.75	0.00554	0.05447	0.84328	39.094	15.534	31.535
Fluoxetine	15.632	273.628	116.723	983.518	1	2.25	0.02601	0.004	0.84967	31.967	8.854	13.433
Naringin	329.671	170.767	0	1452.75	7	19.3	0.05036	0.07138	0.86717	45.269	16.686	37.186
Fiestin	241.075	255.747	0	835.918	4	5.5	0.02711	0.02214	0.86379	27.173	10.36	18.473
Scutellarin	385.621	253.299	0	1238.68	5	12.3	0.03841	0.03949	0.80091	40.058	15.398	28.688
Miquelianin	416.294	187.965	0	1218.36	6	13.05	0.03594	0.04789	0.82654	37.979	15.158	29.898
isorhamnetin	231.152	209.302	0	909.865	3	5.25	0.04014	0.01713	0.85539	29.047	10.432	17.551
luteolin	249.597	253.136	0	843.322	3	4.5	0.07829	0.0155	0.85866	27.445	10.222	17.301
Vitexin	341.98	234.034	0	1205.89	6	12.25	0.07862	0.04503	0.82216	39.204	14.845	30.231
Apigenin	203.554	290.684	0	824.26	2	3.75	0.04896	0.01073	0.86021	27.683	9.75	14.99
chrysin	148.867	331.881	0	800.283	1	3	0.02632	0.00624	0.86711	27.759	9.224	12.691
cynaroside	364.257	211.843	0	1229.16	6	13	0.02966	0.04634	0.80758	38.639	15.08	29.722
naringenin	196.212	249.455	0	834.672	2	4	0.02454	0.01138	0.86225	27.706	9.524	14.702
kameferol	233.623	259.079	0	831.049	3	4.5	0.01562	0.01582	0.86763	27.01	10.076	16.243
Myricetin	326.016	186.581	0	871.362	5	6	0.00359	0.02617	0.86071	26.647	11.037	19.931
Quercetin	281.084	220.788	0	850.688	4	5.25	0.01941	0.02092	0.86514	26.789	10.551	18.213
ombuin	182.425	196.402	0	970.404	2	5.25	0.05172	0.01316	0.83994	31.347	10.311	16.763
wogonin	133.894	290.83	0	870.428	1	3.75	0.04545	0.00739	0.86886	29.532	9.541	13.824
baicalin	321.04	274.121	0	1200.73	4	11.55	0.0452	0.03502	0.82815	39.38	14.476	26.532
quercitrin	338.576	198.071	0	1196.7	6	12.05	0.04162	0.04491	0.82942	37.851	14.48	29.06
wogonin	135.498	292.564	0	875.389	1	3.75	0.01416	0.00734	0.86588	29.747	9.598	13.473
Nobiletin	41.67	134.997	0	1194.96	0	7	0.02402	0	0.83111	39.105	10.563	16.338

Entry Name	QPlog Pw	QPlog Po/w	QPlogS	CIQP logS	QPlog HERG	QPP Caco	QPlog BB	QPP MDCK	QPlog Kp	IP (eV)	EA (eV)	#met ab	QPlogK hsa
Globularicitrin	35.804	-2.34	-2.46	-4.16	-5.607	1.372	-4.564	0.398	-6.942	9.406	0.785	10	-1.317
kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether -3-O-Beta-D-Glucopyranoside	34.037	-2.031	-2.7	-4.208	-5.699	1.126	-4.584	0.322	-7.121	9.215	1.028	9	-1.19
Isoquercetin	26.78	-1.609	-2.546	-4.032	-5.284	1.623	-3.989	0.478	-7.115	8.936	1.072	8	-0.902
hesperidin	32.266	-1.473	-3.094	-4.33	-5.81	3.363	-4.266	1.05	-6.36	9.089	0.705	11	-1.194
Hyperoside	26.614	-1.167	-2.517	-4.032	-5.072	3.395	-3.525	1.06	-6.456	8.884	0.866	8	-0.809
Fluoxetine	5.44	4.623	-4.017	-4.242	-5.996	1756.14	0.742	4385.09	-2.33	9.158	0.127	4	0.605
Naringin	31.239	-1.641	-1.875	-4.067	-4.496	7.407	-3.143	2.464	-5.746	9.314	0.654	10	-1.076
Fiestin	14.688	0.484	-2.708	-3.678	-4.956	51.261	-1.832	19.943	-4.678	8.604	1.036	4	-0.375
Scutellarin	23.194	-0.218	-3.449	-4.611	-4.154	0.553	-3.987	0.19	-6.87	9.364	0.958	7	-0.831
Miquelianin	24.871	-0.932	-2.782	-4.577	-3.428	0.283	-4.102	0.092	-7.57	9.457	1.042	8	-0.953
isorhamnetin	12.455	1.18	-3.222	-4.401	-4.87	63.663	-1.844	25.206	-4.562	8.489	0.817	5	-0.169
luteolin	12.293	0.962	-3.082	-4.073	-5.026	42.557	-1.935	16.309	-4.844	8.992	0.846	4	-0.189
Vitexin	24.33	-0.698	-3.221	-4.035	-5.526	5.661	-3.292	1.843	-6.23	9.126	0.64	9	-0.654
Apigenin	10.232	1.654	-3.401	-4.101	-5.18	116.306	-1.451	48.348	-3.959	9.233	1.025	3	-0.024
chrysin	8.125	2.39	-3.653	-4.123	-5.265	383.877	-0.877	175.756	-2.902	9.243	0.873	2	0.14
cynaroside	24.678	-1.033	-3.027	-4.066	-5.656	3.481	-3.763	1.089	-6.526	9.118	0.767	7	-0.814
naringenin	10.155	1.632	-3.391	-3.927	-4.951	136.529	-1.377	57.495	-3.969	9.25	0.599	5	-0.032
kameferol	12.2	1.014	-2.923	-4.073	-4.909	60.319	-1.747	23.778	-4.528	8.55	0.791	4	-0.211
Myricetin	16.349	-0.318	-2.421	-4.011	-4.676	8.022	-2.732	2.686	-6.295	9.011	1.111	6	-0.501
Quercetin	14.267	0.33	-2.65	-4.043	-4.767	21.398	-2.242	7.757	-5.442	8.609	1.026	5	-0.361
ombuin	10.652	2.02	-3.861	-4.751	-5.058	184.487	-1.462	79.606	-3.71	8.77	0.683	5	0.019
wogonin	8.326	2.589	-3.718	-4.447	-5.041	532.338	-0.8	250.26	-2.675	9.108	0.992	3	0.15
baicalin	20.825	0.472	-3.263	-4.635	-3.813	2.265	-3.039	0.871	-5.703	9.325	0.888	6	-0.707
quercitrin	23.623	-0.684	-2.977	-4.38	-5.237	6.098	-3.26	1.997	-6.198	9.425	0.737	7	-0.674
wogonin	8.357	2.61	-3.783	-4.447	-5.097	514.013	-0.822	240.961	-2.698	9.029	0.951	3	0.162
Nobiletin	8.069	3.552	-3.992	-5.331	-4.909	3987.93	-0.2	2206.42	-1.236	8.912	0.889	6	-0.04

Entry Name	Human Oral Absorption	Percent Human Oral Absorption	SA fluorine	SA amideO	PSA	#NandO	Rule of Five	Rule Of Three	#ring atoms	#in 34	#in 56
Globularicitrin	1	0	0	0	258.776	16	3	2	28	0	28
kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether - 3-O-Beta-D-Gluco pyranoside	1	0	0	0	249.846	15	3	2	28	0	28
Isoquercetin	1	0	0	0	218.632	12	2	2	22	0	22
hesperidin	1	0	0	0	236.488	15	3	2	28	0	28
Hyperoside	1	3.696	0	0	215.618	12	2	2	22	0	22
Fluoxetine	3	100	116.723	0	16.801	2	0	0	12	0	12
Naringin	1	0	0	0	224.184	14	3	2	28	0	28
Fiestin	3	60.379	0	0	119.224	6	0	0	16	0	16
Scutellarin	1	0	0	0	220.523	12	2	2	22	0	22
Miquelianin	1	0	0	0	235.416	13	2	2	22	0	22
isorhamnetin	3	66.139	0	0	124.684	7	0	0	16	0	16
luteolin	3	61.736	0	0	121.168	6	0	0	16	0	16
Vitexin	2	23.374	0	0	186.607	10	1	2	22	0	22
Apigenin	3	73.601	0	0	100.462	5	0	0	16	0	16
chrysin	3	87.194	0	0	77.406	4	0	0	16	0	16
cynaroside	1	4.671	0	0	197.721	11	2	2	22	0	22
naringenin	3	74.715	0	0	98.267	5	0	0	16	0	16
kameferol	3	64.749	0	0	117.088	6	0	0	16	0	16
Myricetin	2	28.307	0	0	159.718	8	1	1	16	0	16
Quercetin	2	52.688	0	0	138.705	7	0	1	16	0	16
ombuin	3	79.332	0	0	112.924	7	0	0	16	0	16
wogonin	3	90.9	0	0	82.233	5	0	0	16	0	16
baicalin	1	10.149	0	0	198.733	11	2	1	22	0	22
quercitrin	2	11.074	0	0	196.805	11	2	2	22	0	22
wogonin	3	90.751	0	0	83.216	5	0	0	16	0	16
Nobiletin	3	100	0	0	78.051	8	0	0	16	0	16

Entry Name	#noncon	#nonHatm	Jm
Globularicitrin	10	43	0
kameferol 7,4 Dimethyl Ether -3-O-Beta-D-Gluco pyranoside	10	42	0
Isoquercetin	5	33	0
hesperidin	12	43	0
Hyperoside	5	33	0
Fluoxetine	0	22	0.139
Naringin	12	41	0.014
Fiestin	0	21	0.012
Scutellarin	5	33	0
Miquelianin	5	34	0
isorhamnetin	0	23	0.005
luteolin	0	21	0.003
Vitexin	5	31	0
Apigenin	0	20	0.012
chrysin	0	19	0.071
cynaroside	5	32	0
naringenin	2	20	0.012
kamepferol	0	21	0.01
Myricetin	0	23	0.001
Quercetin	0	22	0.002
ombuin	0	24	0.009
wogonin	0	21	0.115
baicalin	5	32	0
quercitrin	5	32	0
wogonin	0	21	0.094
Nobiletin	0	29	2.38